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The Contribution of Coherence Relations to Understanding Paratactic Forms of Communication in Social Media Comment Sections

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Abstract

In this article, our aim is to explore how coherence relations can be leveraged to identify discursive strategies, in particular, parataxis; that generate pragmatic-stylistic effects. This is done by making use of computational linguistics tools to analyze immigration-related discourse within the SFU Opinion and Comments (SOCC) corpus. Within our methodology, an NLP-based discourse parser is first used for the automated extraction and identification of coherence relations within comment sections. This information is then subjected to qualitative analysis, aiming to identify paratactic forms of communication that can be understood as typical formations reflecting a larger grammar of coherence relation for social media related content.

Keywords: rhetorical structure theory, discourse coherence, discourse parser, implicit connectives, parataxis, joint relations

1. Introduction

Major news platforms have recently ended the use of their comment sections due to challenges in moderating spam and political feuding. Notably, discourse analysts such as Verschueren (2021) observe that communication on social media no longer serves to provide information that matters but is more about luring users into engaging with content. In this article, our aim is to explore how coherence relations can be leveraged to identify discursive strategies, in particular parataxis, that generate pragmatic-stylistic effects. This is done by examining paratactic communication style that mimics a logical-argumentative flow by presenting a series of implicitly related statements, leading to a climactic consequence.

Our method consists of using an NLP-based discourse parser to automatically extract patterns of coherence relations which fit the description of the discursive strategies mentioned above. While no large-scale evaluation has been conducted, we illustrate that system outputs for JOINT coherence relations can be used to identify cases where sentences or independent clauses are combined to form paratactic structures. From these foundational structures, our analysis progresses to delineate specific patterns of coherence relations, which may potentially be associated with the typical formations of a grammar of coherence relations for social media related content.

2. Parataxis in Social Media

In social media research, especially focusing on micro-blogging, forums, and comment sections, parataxis has become a noteworthy area of study. Parataxis can be described as a style of communication, whether written or spoken, characterized by the assembly of short sentences without the aid of connectives, relying instead on implicit connections between the sentences.

Scholars frequently examine implicitness in research on persuasion and rhetoric or in hate speech detection. Typically, they analyze the discursive structure of specific comments or tweets, examining the associated behaviors such as stance or the use of contentious language within the context of political discourse (de Rijk, 2020; Gabrielova et al., 2021; Theye and Melling, 2018). It is crucial to highlight that while implicitness is commonly associated with unspoken claims or statements deliberately left unsaid, the implicitness examined in our study pertains to the absence of explicit connectives or syntactic elements that link independent clauses.

Previous studies observe that while implicitness commonly occurs in language and in regular social interactions, in the context of political discourse implicit ways of conveying meaning is often associated with political feuding, hate speech or disinformation. In a discourse analysis of disinformation tweets surrounding the corona-5G-conspiracy, de Rijk (2020) uses Speech Act Theory (Searle, 1965) to show that users tweeting misinformative content often communicate through indirect speech acts and by omitting connectives between sentences. As for parataxis, it has been examined in a study by Theye and Melling (2018), wherein this mode of communication is often viewed as a means of expressing "straight talk" that is liberated from the constraints of political correctness. The authors of this study also show that parataxis encourages a type of communication that avoids the requirement for providing evidence and explanations.

In this paper we propose a method for performing a similar type of analysis by making use of coherence relations as they can help us interpret paratactic forms of communication.

3. Method: RST Theory and Discourse Parsers

Coherence relations account for text organization by means of relations that hold between text segments. In this article we use Rhetorical Structure Theory (RST; Mann and Thompson, 1988) as a text-analytical model of coherence relations. With RST, relations between text segments are annotated with different classes of coherence relations such as ELABORATION, CONTRAST, CAUSAL, TEMPORAL, etc. The text segments of an RST tree are "elementary discourse units" (EDUs), which are contiguous spans of tokens roughly similar to clauses. Relations are made not only between text segments but between groups of text segments, meaning that the final RST representation of a full text (book, chapter, article, comment etc.) is a hierarchical tree of text segments connected by coherence relations.

While coherence relations from RST have been used in cognitive linguistics studies of textual processing and in discourse parsing, their application in political discourse analysis has been limited. Yet some political discourse analysts have found RST relations to be relevant, from using them as discourse pragmatic functions to analyze the structure of policy-setting segments in US presidential inaugurals (Cap, 2002; Windt, 1994) to studying how the strategic use of patterns of coherence relations enhance a speaker's ethos (Cap, 2021). We should also note that RST discourse characteristics have been incorporated as features in transformer-based architectures for automatically recognizing persuasive techniques and obtained considerable results (Chernyavskiy et al., 2024).

Our focus lies in exploring how particular coherence relations can be used to gain insight into paratactic forms of communication. Specifically, we are interested in understanding how these relations are signaled—whether through discourse markers, syntax, semantic cues, lexical cues, and so forth.

3.1. *The SOCC Corpus*

The dataset used in our research is the SFU Opinion and Comments Corpus (SOCC; Kolhatkar et al., 2020), a corpus designed for the analysis of online news commentary. This corpus contains both comments and the articles from the main Canadian daily in English, *The Globe and Mail*. The articles are opinion pieces and have been curated to maintain reply structures and other metadata. In our experiments, we focus on a subset of this dataset containing 32 articles and their associated comments (approximately 3800 in total), which were selected as they exclusively address immigration in Europe. The size of this subset is approximately 220,000 tokens.

It is worth mentioning that the subset was created for our focus on studying social media discourse related to immigration. The analysis presented in this article emerged from exploratory research conducted on this dataset; thus, this dataset was not specifically tailored to align with the kinds of phenomena described here.

3.2. *DMRST Discourse Parser*

The experimental configuration initially replicates the DMRST parser developed by Liu et al. (2021). This system, operating as a top-down multilingual parser, simultaneously manages text segmentation and RST tree parsing. Its relevance to our study stems from its state-of-the-art performance in predicting coherence relation labels. The authors have made a well-trained model accessible through a model checkpoint optimized for inference. This specific model was trained on a multilingual dataset of RST discourse treebanks, providing native support for six languages: English, Portuguese, Spanish, German, Dutch, and Basque.

The parser was executed on articles and comments separately, resulting in a single RST tree output for each article and individual comment. The parsing process involved segmenting every comment and article into textual segments (or EDUs), followed by the generation of an RST tree representation.

4. Coherence Relation of Interest: JOINT Relation

In this section we proceed to a description of JOINT relations extracted by the parser, illustrating how they can be considered as cohesive textual elements. The three grammatical structures described here are derived from Quirk and Crystal (2010) and aim to demonstrate how coherence between two segments of text united by the JOINT relation is achieved. This will offer us a clearer understanding of the types of discursive structures we are focusing on.

4.1. *Asyndetic connection*

Asyndetic connection refers to the juxtaposition of sentences such as in (1) which share no grammatical or lexical characteristics.

- (1) “[Keep stirring that pot.] ←*joint*→ [Divide and concur.]” **SOCC:**
28117977_200

In (1), even though the two sentences are unrelated, the connection is made clear: we comprehend that this comment implies a particular theory where immigration serves the unclear conquering interests of the government. Asyndetic constructions such as this one typically get the reader to speculate on the possible connections between the sentences, even if

they might be none. We also note here that if we reverse the order of the sentences the perceived connection is the same.

4.2. Structural Parallelism

Other text segments united by JOINT in our data can also be described by structural parallelism. The impression of connection here is achieved by putting together sentences which share grammatical characteristics such as tense, aspect, clause structure or word order. In (2) here the parallelism is syntactic and lexical.

(2) “[Christians in.] ←*joint*→ [Muslims out.]” SOCC: 24040902_18

4.3. Connection by Sequence

Similar to structural parallelism, segments of text linked by sequence share common grammatical characteristics. However, connections based on sequence imply a temporal or causal relation, depicting real world events.

(3) “[Dry them off,]
←*joint*→ [give them a hot meal]
←*joint*→ [and re-send them a Muslim country.]” SOCC: 24036827_1

In connections based on sequences where a narrative is presented, we typically observe that the tense of the verbs remains consistent, and the sequence follows a regular chronological order. In examples where three or more sentences/clauses are juxtaposed by JOINT relations, the last element of the sequence often carries a climactic effect. It is likely to be introduced by the discourse marker *and* which aims to emphasize an inevitable conclusive point. This also results in sequences that, despite lacking temporal aspects, still generate a logical or consequential flow:

(4) “[East is east,]
←*joint*→ [West is west,]
←*joint*→ [and the two shall never meet.]” SOCC: 26338254_193_1

5. Analysis of Patterns of Coherence Relations

From these fundamental grammatical processes that connect segments of text into a coherent flow, we observe that a particular pattern of coherence emerges in the comments section of our dataset.

As we have seen, triadic sequences hold a special implication in that they not only suggest a sequential flow of reasoning but also develop to establish a climactic consequence. Consecutive text segments held together by JOINT relations which follow this particular scheme are indeed frequent. In cases involving patterns only containing 5 EDUs, 11% of the sequences of coherence relations found in comments (and only 0.03% in articles) fit the pattern *JOINT JOINT X*, where *X* can be any of the coherence relations extracted by the DMRST parser.

Here we focus on cases where the final element of the sequence is introduced by an EVALUATION relation. This pattern is characterized by 2 or 3 text segments united by JOINT relations, with a last text segment connected by an EVALUATION relation. The EVALUATION relation consists in directing the reader’s attention towards a main point (the nucleus in RST theory). It can either be evidential with the intention of increasing the reader’s belief in the nuclear material, or justifying with the intention of increasing “the reader's readiness to accept the writer's right to present the nuclear material” (Mann and Thompson, 1988). While the JOINT relation is multinuclear, the EVALUATION relation is mononuclear, meaning that the relation includes only one segment featuring a main claim and, in our case, it is a subjective evaluation (positive/negative, desirable/undesirable) from the writer's perspective (Stede et al., 2017).

This last segment is usually the main important claim or climactic statement. The segments under study here follow the extraction schemes represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: RST trees of extracted patterns of coherence relations. Where either a joint has another JOINT as a left child and EVALUATION as right child or an EVALUATION has a joint left child which in turn has either a left or right JOINT child.

Upon running the parser and extracting sequences that match these patterns, we have successfully identified instances such as the following:

- (5) “[Put everybody in a refugee camp for few years,
 ←*joint*→ [allow only legit refugees in,
 ←*joint*→ [send everyone else back.]
 evaluation→ [Problem solved.]” SOCC: 25120537_0

Again, this sort of paratactic structure evokes the sense of a build up towards a conclusive endpoint. In (5) the comment depicts a narrative with a consequential structure built on syntactic parallelism. The first three text segments all start with a verb and present the same clause structure while the concluding statement employs a present perfect tense, which indicates a perfective aspect. What is significant to highlight is that there is a noticeable break in the stylistic flow of coherence, which serves to isolate, with stylistic emphasis, the final sentence. Here this kind of build up suggests a sequential flow with a natural conclusive point which has the aim of suggesting that the solution to immigration is simple and that actual policies are evasive.

The discernible interruption in the coherence flow, aimed at accentuating the final sentence, is accomplished through various strategies. One of the most common methods involves introducing the third textual segment with the discourse marker *and* as demonstrated in the following example:

- (6) “[Most immigrants are not even interviewed by visa officers anymore.]
 ←*joint*→ [Their consultants produce "perfect" applications for them]
 ←*joint*→ [and they sail through on paper.]
evaluation→ [The system is out of control.]” SOCC: 26338254_0_4_0

By inserting an *and* at this juncture, the comment indicates the conclusion of this portion of the discourse and establishes a pause before delivering the climactic point, typically in the form of a concise and epigrammatic statement.

Another frequent and effective method of disrupting the flow of coherence is through the use of rhetorical questions. In (7), the evaluative statement presented as a question disrupts the flow by prompting the reader towards a conclusion. Here again, this interruption occurs after a micro-narrative built with a syntactic parallelism.

- (7) “[We went there with the best intention, along with a big NATO force]
 ←*joint*→ [spent many billions]
 ←*joint*→ [lost some of Canada's best,]
evaluation→ [and what was achieved??]” SOCC: 25851989_0_4_0

6. Proposal for Targeted Parser Evaluation

In this section, we propose an evaluation of the parsers' performance in extracting the *JOINT JOINT EVALUATION* coherence relation patterns as described in Figure 1. Our aim here is to ensure that not only were the identified cases of *JOINT JOINT EVALUATION* successfully recognized (precision), but also to gain an understanding of how many cases the parser missed by confusing them with other relations (recall). To achieve this, we extracted 161 cases of *JOINT JOINT X* (which also included 17 cases of *JOINT JOINT EVALUATION*), where *X* represents any other coherence relation label. Furthermore, we retained only cases containing 4 EDUs, as these formations best fit the descriptions of the paratactic phenomena we discussed earlier. We then annotated these cases, focusing exclusively on whether an *EVALUATION* relation was present or not. Prior to reaching a consensus, the inter-annotation agreement Cohen's kappa score was 0.64. The performance results of the DMRST parser are shown below:

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
<i>Not Joint Joint Evaluation</i>	0.70	1.00	0.82	101
<i>Joint Joint Evaluation</i>	1.00	0.28	0.44	60
Accuracy			0.73	161
Weighted Avg	0.81	0.73	0.68	161

Table 1: DMRST parser's overall performance for recognizing the JOINT JOINT EVALUATION

The global results are encouraging. All 17 instances of *JOINT JOINT EVALUATION* that were identified are indeed correct. However, as expected, the parser failed to identify 43 actual cases, which explains the low recall. Therefore, we present the types of patterns with which the *JOINT JOINT EVALUATION* pattern was most frequently confused.

Pattern type	# cases	# actual evaluation cases
<i>Joint Joint Joint</i>	71	22
<i>Joint Joint Elaboration</i>	16	5
<i>Joint Joint Background</i>	11	5
<i>Joint Joint Explanation</i>	9	3
<i>Joint Joint Condition</i>	6	2
<i>Joint Joint Temporal</i>	2	2

Table 2: Types of patterns with which the JOINT JOINT EVALUATION was confused most

What we observe here is that the *EVALUATION* relation is often confused with the *JOINT*, *BACKGROUND* and *ELABORATION* relations. The reason for this is that these relations are indicated by similar signals which, for some cases, can cause confusion in the relation label recognition process (Pastor and Oostdijk, 2024).

7. Discussion

As demonstrated in the preceding sections, the texts identified using the patterns outlined in Figure 1 do indeed align with a paratactic scheme of textual organization. We suggest that further research should aim to contextualize this finding in relation to how this particular discursive strategy attempts to bypass what psychologists refer to as the *forewarning effect*. Kamalski et al. (2008) have investigated this effect by examining coherence relations, revealing that *forewarning* factors such as employing syntactic and explicit cues to connect textual segments, can lead to resistance to persuasion. While non-implicit forms of signaling coherence relations help with reading comprehension in informative texts, in persuasive texts, the use of connectives contributes to the reader's resistance, as the reader recognizes that they are being persuaded.

This effect has also been studied in research directly involving parataxis with the concept of *charge of device*. In a similar manner to the *forewarning effect*, Perelman and Olbrechts-Tyteca (1969) describe it as “the impression that a device is being used when the speaker seems to adopt rules or techniques which, because they are too uniform or too far fetched, do not seem to fit the object in an altogether natural manner.” On the other hand, parataxis is perceived as unburdened by any charge of device, as it generates a rapid sequence of loosely connected statements that appear spontaneous. Theye and Melling (2018) observe that paratactic forms of communication create an impression of sincerity, suggesting that the speaker or writer is speaking candidly. In political discourse, this fosters the perception that complex problems can be resolved with a one-line solution, often presented as a natural conclusion arising from a consequential flow of implicitly connected statements.

A promising perspective would be to demonstrate that the type of paratactic communication presented in this article is linked to persuasive techniques or serves only to create pragmatic-stylistic effects such as irony or humor.

8. Limitations

It is important to mention that the parser was trained on newswire data and has not seen any training examples coming from comment sections. Much progress remains to be made in improving the current parser for our specific goals. Some straightforward solutions could entail training on corpora specifically sourced from social media data and comment sections. Additionally, effectively managing class imbalances would lead to improved performance for the recognition of the relations we are interested in.

9. Conclusion

Automatically identifying patterns of coherence relations remains a challenging task, and there is a need for improving current discourse parsing systems. However, the outputs generated by these systems show promise, as they accurately capture patterns that align with clear instances of paratactic communication aimed at creating pragmatic-stylistic effects. As demonstrated here, this effect involves presenting a consequential flow of implicitly related statements that culminate in a climactic point. We have also discerned how this is achieved through grammatical characteristics such as structural parallelism, sequential connection, and the use of connectives, which are closely linked to the patterns of coherence relation patterns of interest.

Future research will explore the extent to which the presented discursive strategies are prevalent in comment sections. Additionally, it will further evaluate the performance of discourse parsers in analyzing these structures to determine the feasibility of automating such analyses. Finally, we find it promising to analyze the extent to which these discursive strategies are associated with persuasive techniques or with pragmatic effects, such as humor or irony.

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